

FROM CLASSROOM DEMANDS TO BURNOUT: EXPLORING JOB PERFORMANCE AND LOCUS OF CONTROL AS DETERMINANTS OF EMOTIONAL EXHAUSTION

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Abstract

The current teachers have a critical role to play in creating conducive learning and contributing to student achievement far beyond the conventional responsibility of teaching lessons. Yet, teachers are often exposed to conditions which can cause them emotional fatigue because of the intensification of their profession. The purpose of the present research is to study the relation between teachers' emotional exhaustion and their locus of control as well as job performance. The study was conducted in the various institution of Punjab; a sample of 300 teachers were selected. Demographic factors such as gender, family structure, residence area, teaching experiences (years), academic background, range of monthly salary and grade were also considered while examining the variables. For the survey study design, participants were recruited using a simple sampling method. Job performance, locus of control and emotional exhaustion were operationalized through Job Performance (Erdogan & Enders, 2007), Multidimensional Locus of Control (Levenson, 1981) Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) (Delgado, et al., 2018). Psychometric properties and descriptive were determined to make sure the normality of sample. Regression analysis revealed that job performance and internal locus of control negatively predict emotional exhaustion and positively predict by external locus of control Implications of the current research were discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers bear greater significance with respect to educational results in rapidly adapting learning environments, yet teaching has a high emotional burden, which may result in emotional exhaustion as one of the major components of occupational stress. Emotional exhaustion leads to less job satisfaction, lower levels of teaching efficacy, and increased odds for leaving the career effectively a major sustainability issue within education (Voss et al., 2023). Task proficiency, which includes in-role behavior, such as

activities made to accomplish work obligations, is a component of job performance (Piercy et al., 2006). An intense feeling of emotional fatigue brought on by accumulating pressures from either the personal or professional spheres, or both, is known as emotional exhaustion. Emotional exhaustion is one feels the signs of burnout (Cafasso, 2019). Locus of control defines the approach of individuals into their lives. It is style of thinking and perception through which individuals understand the causality of events. The

fact that life events are controlled by either the person itself or influenced by many other elements such as fate, chance, or luck is known as locus of control. Locus of control holds two dimensions. Internal locus of control is the conviction that our own choices and efforts are responsible for the results of events.

Job Performance

One of the main concept in industrial or organizational psychology is job performance (Austin & Villanova, 1992). Degree of efficacy and efficiency demonstrated at the moment of achieving the individuals' aims and objectives (Khoshnaw & Alavi, 2020). Understanding the notion of job performance is essential to comprehending the many strategies and interventions that industrial organizational psychology (I-O psychology) may use to increase worker productivity. Recruitment, selection, training, development, and incentives are all strategies for improving the performance of a company.

Campbell's Model of Performance

Campbell's Model of Performance (1990) is one of the most elementary frameworks in organizational psychology, which further divides job performance into measurable components and shows the major determinants of performance.

Determinants of job performance. Campbell said that performance is determined by the following three major factors:

Declarative Knowledge. Facts, principles, and procedures related to the job. Example: Having in your mind company policies or a sequence of the production line.

Procedural knowledge and skill. It is the capability to correctly apply declarative knowledge in practical settings. Includes motor skills, cognitive skills, and physical tasks.

Motivation. The effort and determination which the individual puts into their job. Motivation affects how much knowledge and skill there is to apply for the performance.

Campbell found eight job performance dimensions applicable to a great number of roles.

- i. Task-specific job competence.
- ii. Non-task specific-job performance.
- iii. Ability to Write and Speak Effectively.
- iv. Effort shown

- v. Keep personal discipline
- vi. Facilitate peer-to-peer and team performance
- vii. Supervision and Leadership
- viii. Management/Administration

Vroom's Expectancy Theory of Motivation

Vroom's Expectancy Theory (1964) describes how people use expectancies and rewards to guide their decisions to maximize their performance and effort. Vroom's Expectancy Theory highlights three factors that drive performance

Expectancy (Effort → Performance). An idea that a person should attain a preferred performance level as per the efforts he put in doing so (Permazadian & Shen, 2024).

Instrumentality (Performance → Reward). The idea that good performance will lead to a specific outcome or reward (Astyandini, et al., 2024).

Valence (Value of Rewards). Value an individual place on the rewards they receive. Incentives may be substantial (e.g., salary, bonuses) or intangible (e.g., recognition, career growth) (Sobaih, et al., 2024).

Locus of Control

Locus of control defines the approach of individuals into their lives. It is style of thinking and perception through which individuals understand the causality of events. Locus of control is the belief about one's life events are controlled by you or the forces such as chance, luck, or fate (Boyd & Zimbardo, 2005). Locus of control is a mental idea that catches people's convictions about the causal connection between their own conduct and life occasions (Clark et al., 2016).

Dimension of Attributions Theory

According to Weiner the reasons that we assign to our actions will affect how we will act in the future (Weiner, 2010).

Locus of Control (Causality). The emotions connected to this attribution are directly impacted by a learner's perception of control, which in turn influences their belief in the motive behind their actions (Weiner, 2010).

Stability (instability). The probability that the source of attribution will shift over time, this suggests unpredictability as the person could ultimately impact the outcome by developing their talents and accumulating experience. By altering behaviors, it is possible to change the circumstance, which is not permanent (Weiner, 1972).

Controllability (uncontrollability). It has a direct bearing on how to control the person's feels of the activity, behavior, or circumstance. It would be beyond their control (Weiner, 2010).

Types of Locus of Control

The notion of internal and exterior loci of control was first proposed by Rotter in the 1950s.

Internal Locus of Control. It is a belief that outcomes of events are because of our own decision and effort. When a person thinks he or she should act to maximize the likelihood of good results and reduce the probability of bad results, it is assumed that he or she has an internal control locus.

External Locus of Control. This is the belief that outcomes of events are externally controlled and depend upon luck, chance or fate. The individuals who are consistently helpless before karma, destiny and unexpected uncontrollable external power and feel defenseless constantly and never prefer to assume the liability for their awful results and hopeless exhibitions in life are said to have external locus of control (Sherman et al., 2005).

Emotional Exhaustion

The majority of the research on emotional exhaustion focuses on burnout and work satisfaction. People who engage in "people-work" frequently develop burnout, which is defined as emotional tiredness and cynicism. Furthermore, it has been defined as a persistent condition of diminished emotional reserves brought on by demanding occupations. The stress condition known as emotional exhaustion is caused by ongoing interpersonal and emotional stress at work (Augner & Schermuly, 2023).

Types of Emotional Exhaustion

Emotional exhaustion can manifest in various forms depending on the context or underlying causes. Common types include:

Work Related Emotional Exhaustion. Caused by disagreements, a heavy workload, a lack of support, or ongoing workplace stress. Frequently observed in occupations like healthcare, education, and customer service that demand a lot of emotional work (Maslach & Jackson, 1981).

Relationship-Induced Emotional Exhaustion. Resulting from toxic dynamics, difficult personal relationships, or caring obligations, frequent when there is emotional dependence or an imbalanced give-and-take (Pines, 2013).

Parental Emotional Exhaustion. Experienced by parents or other caregivers who feel overburdened by the responsibilities of childrearing, particularly under trying conditions. There may be overlap with the term "parental burnout" (Mikolajczak et al., 2019).

Chronic Illness or Trauma-Related Emotional Exhaustion. Connected to healing from trauma or managing long-term health conditions. Exhaustion might result from prolonged mental and emotional effort to handle health or prior traumas (Figley, 2013).

Compassion Fatigue. A particular type of emotional exhaustion commonly experienced by caregivers or helping professionals. It is a product of being exposed to other people's pain too long and the loss of ability to empathize (Stamm, 2005).

Theoretical background

Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory. The Conservation of Resources Theory, put forth by Stevan Hobfoll in 1989. COR hypothesis is a psychological hypothesis that focuses on the acquisition, depletion, and preservation of valuable resources in order to explain how people manage stress, COR Theory's core ideas include

Resources. Assets that are valued from material, social, personal, and energetic sources to help achieve objectives and prevent the negative impacts of stress.

Stress and Resource Loss. Stress is brought on by loss, the potential of loss, or the inability to make a profit from resource investment. Gain is weaker than loss.

Resource Investment. People make investments to guard against loss, recover resources that have been lost and acquire new ones.

Resource Spirals.

Loss Spiral: More vulnerability and loss follow from loss.

Gain spiral: More gains follow the acquisition of resources.

Principles. Primacy of Resource Loss: Resource loss is disproportionately more significant than resource gain.

Resource Investment. Individuals use existing resources to protect themselves and gain more resources.

According to the COR theory, people will feel uncomfortable and subsequently try to reduce losses by working less or leaving their job, people will experience emotional exhaustion if they believe they lack the emotional capacity to handle interpersonal pressures. In general, the COR model of emotional exhaustion emphasizes the importance of an imbalance between effort and rewards (Hills, 2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The nexus of inspiration, performance in tasks, an inventive approach and mental burnout is dynamic and dependent on each other. Teachers who are motivated to innovate and perform well are overachievers and can experience increased stress in trying to achieve set targets which can lead to burnout (Moghaddasi et al., 2024). An investigation of high school teachers in Indonesia showed that locus of control had direct positive influences on work motivation and performance (Virgana & Lapasau, 2024). In the same way, data from Australian panel studies have shown that employees with an internal LOC had high adaptive performance in work settings

which were changed (Nguyen et al., 2022). The most common form of a breakdown of the functioning state is emotional exhaustion (Maslach & Leiter, 2016) which mainly has its origin in high work demands and high-performance pressure. As for professors who feel immensely pressured to perform and have heavy workloads, studies show they suffer from higher levels of fatigue, lower energy and emotional distancing (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2021). Individuals who have an internal LOC are more resilient, pro-active copers who experience less burnout because they believe that they can influence outcomes through their own actions. On the other hand, when they encounter stressful working conditions, those who possess an external LOC (i.e., they believe that what happens to them is due simply to fate, luck or external forces) register more feelings of helplessness and emotional exhaustion (Ng et al., 2006).

Rationale

This study intended to test the influence of locus of control and job performance on teachers' emotional exhaustion. Although previous research has enhanced our understanding of work stress and burnout, there are few studies that focus on the specific challenges encountered by teachers in balancing heavy workloads, administrative responsibilities and student-centered roles all of which could contribute to feelings of emotional exhaustion. The locus of control concept, which has been widely researched in the field of organizational behavior and psychology, seems to be underemployed in educational research for understanding teacher burnout. Available evidence suggests that internal control more likely leads to active coping and resilience in response to stress, while an external orientation may lead to fatigue. Examining how job performance and locus of control contribute to emotional tiredness is crucial for creating solutions that promote teachers' well-being and long-term effectiveness, especially considering the demanding and quickly changing nature of the teaching profession.

Conceptual Framework

Following is the conceptual framework of the present study.

Figure 1. Model showing the predictor and outcome and moderator of current study

Objectives

The present research was conducted in order to achieve subsequent literature goals: The aim of study is to examine

1. The relationship between job performance, locus of control and emotional exhaustion among teachers in educational settings.
2. How job performance and locus of control predict emotional exhaustion.
3. The role of demographic variables (gender, family system, teaching level.)

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were postulated based on objectives:

1. Job performance would be a negative predictor of emotional exhaustion.
2. Internal locus of control would be a negative predictor of emotional exhaustion.
3. External locus of control would be a positive predictor of emotional exhaustion.
4. There are significant demographic differences with reference to the variables of the current study.

Operational Definitions

All constructions were assessed with the help of standardized instruments which are discussed in detail below

Job Performance. Job performance refers to how effectively an individual fulfills the tasks and responsibilities associated with their role (Campbell, 1990).

Locus of Control. The internal external control construct refers to a generalized expectancy that outcomes are either contingent on one's own actions (internal control) or influenced by external forces such as chance, fate, or powerful others (external control) (Levenson, 1981).

Emotional Exhaustion. As a result of high stress and demands placed in a working environment, emotional exhaustion is developed. In the workplace, people who experience such could often note detachment from work emotionally, fatigue and a lack of effectiveness. Emotional exhaustion can be noted as one of the primary factors in an individual exhibiting a burn out (Maslach & Jackson, 1981).

5. METHOD

Research Design and Sample

In order to find out job performance and locus of control impacts emotional exhaustions among teachers. Survey research design was used. The technique used to select the sample of (N = 300) teachers was convenient sampling technique.

Measures

There are three scales which would be used in our study:

Job Performance(Erdogan, & Enders, 2007).

Erdogan and Enders (2007) used a 7-item self-report scale to measure job performance. The items were rated on a 7-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 7 denoting "strongly agree." The scale evaluates competency, task fulfillment, and overall performance.

Multidimensional Locus of Control (Levenson, 1981).

A 24-item Multidimensional Locus of Control Scale, with 1 denoting strongly disagree and 6 denoting strongly agree, was created by Levenson (1981). Three dimensions are evaluated by the scale: Chance (items 2, 6, 7, 10, 12, 14, 16, 24), Powerful Others (items 3, 8, 11, 13, 15, 17, 20, 22), and Internal Locus of

Control (items 1, 4, 5, 9, 18, 19, 21, 23). The External Locus of Control is represented by Chance and Powerful Others combined, whereas the Internal dimension represents personal control (Levenson, 1981).

Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) (Delgado, et al., 2018)

The Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) is a psychometric tool used to assess burnout in individuals in a variety of work environments. It considers the idea of disengagement from work as well as the physical and cognitive elements of exhaustion. The scale is sixteen item having response pattern of 4-point Likert scale (1= strongly agree to 4= strongly disagree) (Delgado, et al., 2018).

Ethical Consideration and Procedure

This study ensures participants’ rights by obtaining informed consent and explaining the study’s purpose and risks. Privacy and confidentiality are strictly maintained through secure data handling. Participants will be treated respectfully and ethically, with proper citation of sources to avoid plagiarism. The research aims to responsibly advance knowledge of abusive supervision and its effects. Data was collected from schools and colleges in Sargodha after obtaining institutional permission. Participants were informed, consented, and assured confidentiality. Demographic data was collected before administering scales. Using purposive convenience sampling, 300 Teachers were selected, categorized by gender, family system and teaching level.

6. RESULTS

Table 1

Pearson Correlation among the Variables of Present Study (N = 300)

Variables	1	2	3	4	α	M	SD	Skewness
1	-				0.74	34.41	7.63	-0.40
2	0.61***	-			0.81	32.0	7.63	-0.24
3	0.40***	0.70***	-		0.87	61.65	11.41	0.90
4	-0.23***	-0.11*	0.02	-	0.76	38.18	6.26	0.14

Note: 1= Job Performance, 2= Internal Locus of Control, 3= External Locus of Control, 4= Emotional Exhaustion
 ***p < .001, **p < .01, * p < .05

Table 2

Regression coefficient of Emotional Exhaustion on Job Performance (N=300)

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	44.61***		1.63
Job Performance	-0.20***	-0.23	0.46
R ²	0.52		

***p < .001

Table 3

Regression coefficient of Emotional Exhaustion on Internal and External Locus of Control (N=300)

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	39.04***		1.75
ILC	-0.17**	-0.21	0.70
ELC	0.08*	0.17	0.04
R ²	0.02		

Note: ILC= Internal Locus of Control, ELC= External Locus of Control
 ***p < .001, **p < .01, * p < .05

Table 4

Mean and Standard Deviation of Present Study Variable with Respect to Gender (N = 300)

Variables	Males (n = 115)		Female (n = 185)		t (298)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
1	32.56	7.73	35.48	7.37	-3.32	.76	-
2	30.76	6.97	34.04	7.76	-3.71	.01	0.44
3	58.48	12.30	63.62	14.13	-3.21	.04	0.40
4	37.86	5.29	38.37	6.68	-0.68	.03	0.08

Note: 1= Job Performance, 2= Internal Locus of Control, 3= External Locus of Control, 4= Emotional Exhaustion
Table 5

Mean and Standard Deviation of Present Study Variable with Respect to Family System (N = 300)

Variables	Joint (n = 184)		Nuclear (n = 116)		t (298)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
1	34.31	7.26	34.43	8.21	-.13	.02	0.01
2	32.40	8.40	33.39	6.20	-1.09	.003	0.13
3	61.16	14.36	62.42	12.51	-.77	.88	-
4	38.32	6.15	37.95	6.59	1.12	.87	-

Note: 1= Job Performance, 2= Internal Locus of Control, 3= External Locus of Control, 4= Emotional Exhaustion

Table 6

Mean, Standard Deviation and F-values for Teaching Level on Current Study Variables (N = 300)

Variables	Primary/Middle (1-8 grade) (n = 113)		Secondary (Grade 9-10) (n = 93)		Intermediate (College) (n = 94)		F (2,297)	η²	Post-Hoc
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
1	36.37	8.21	33.80	7.36	32.50	6.61	7.25**	0.05	1>2>3
2	34.56	9.31	31.69	7.21	31.73	5.03	5.04**	0.03	1>3>2
3	61.55	17.07	60.56	12.85	62.84	9.16	0.64	-	-
4	39.89	7.30	37.68	6.12	37.15	4.61	5.42**	0.03	1>2>3

Note: 1= Job Performance, 2= Internal Locus of Control, 3= External Locus of Control, 4= Emotional Exhaustion
 ***p < .001, **p < .01, * p < .05

7. DISCUSSION

The present study intended to find the effect of job performance and locus of control on emotional exhaustion among teachers. Psychometric qualities of the tools used to estimate various builds were assessed before examining the relationships between the variables in the current examination. The reliability coefficients of the subscales and scales were > .70, This suggests satisfactory internal coherence. The variable of the current study is normally distributed since the values of skewness are within the allowed range, which is less than ±3.

Pearson's correlation results show that job performance has a significant positive correlation with internal locus of control, external locus of control and significantly negative correlation to emotional exhaustion. Internal locus of control has significant positive correlated to external locus of control while negatively correlated to emotional exhaustion. External locus of control shows non-significant correlation as shown (see table 1).

Regression analysis revealed that job performance significantly negatively predicts emotional exhaustion, as better job performance so there will be less

emotional exhaustion, or emotionally exhausted person will have poor job performance. Results are in line with the previous studies (Bhat & Tariq, 2022; Parayitam et al., 2022) so hypothesis 1 is accepted, (see table 2). According to Jorif (2018), burnout is significantly lower in professional school staff with greater internal locus of control, in another study it is revealed that internal locus of control negatively predicts stress as stress is core component of emotional exhaustion or burnout (Malik et al., 2023). The study found that those with an external locus of control are more likely to experience stress at work because they feel more emotionally worn out and think that stresses are out of control (Benveniste et al., 2024). Teachers who have an external locus of control at work are more likely to experience burnout, according to another study (Menter, 2022). Results are in line with the previous studies, henceforth hypothesis 2, internal locus of control negatively predicts emotional exhaustion and hypothesis 3 external locus of control positively predicts emotional exhaustion are accepted. (see table 3).

The study also explored demographic differences, revealing that females scored higher on internal locus, external locus of control and emotional exhaustion, findings are partially parallel to prior researches (Markus et al., 2018). It was shown that although men and women had similar depression scores, women were more emotionally exhausted, had less vigor, and were less vigilant than males. According to Ayesha and Zamir (2021) reported that female university teachers were more externally oriented, while males showed a stronger internal locus. Similar gender-based differences were also observed by Gupta et al. (2018), supporting the current study's findings, (see table 4). Results showed significant family status differences in job performance and internal locus of control. Teachers from nuclear families reported higher job performance, likely due to stronger support and fewer distractions (Nadeem et al., 2023). However, Kaura and Sharma (2015) found that adolescents from joint families had a higher internal locus of control, while those from nuclear families showed more external orientation partially aligning with current findings (see Table 5). The results of the current study exposed that internal locus of control's levels are greater in participants at the primary teaching level, job performance, these findings are constant with other

research showing that the teachers at Pasir Mas District Excellence Cluster Primary School also have strong intrinsic motivation, which influences the school's effectiveness (Khun et al., 2022), Present study also indicates that primary school teachers are more emotionally exhausted, findings are supported by prior studies which states that over a third of primary teachers surveyed displayed burnout, with emotional exhaustion (EE) present in alongside high psychological distress (Ozoemena et al., 2021), (See Table 6).

CONCLUSION

The current study emphasizes how teachers' mental health is significantly shaped by their job performance and locus of control. In particular, teachers with a stronger internal locus of control reported less burnout than those with an external orientation, and higher job performance was associated with less emotional exhaustion. These dynamics were also impacted by demographic variations, including gender, family structure, and teaching level. Overall, the results support the idea that psychological resources such as professional efficacy or better job performance and internal locus of control can serve as buffers against teachers' emotional tiredness.

IMPLICATIONS

These findings are important from a theoretical and practical standpoint. Study contributes to the body of knowledge by showing how locus of control and job performance work together to affect emotional tiredness in educational settings. From a practical standpoint, the results indicate that educational institutions and policymakers ought to contemplate initiatives that enhance educators' self-efficacy, resilience, and sense of internal control. Teachers may be better able to handle stress, sustain performance, and lessen burnout with the support of training programs, mentorship, and wellness initiatives. Differences based on gender and family also emphasize the necessity of context-sensitive policies that take into consideration the varied experiences of teachers.

Teachers respond differently to interventions based on whether they have an internal or external orientation. This calls for school leaders to apply psychological insights and adapt strategies to diverse

teacher profiles. Additionally, significant demographic effects suggest that training and policies must be context-sensitive, addressing specific needs based on gender, experience, and background, promoting a more inclusive and effective teaching environment.

SUGGESTIONS

Considering the findings, a longitudinal study design may be used in the future to capture the change in locus of control, emotional exhaustion, and job performance. The generalizability could also be enhanced by extending the research to other areas and levels of education. At school level, the professional development programs on management and psychological health stress should be funded by the school. Emotional fatigue can potentially decrease further with the help of counseling services and the creation of supportive working conditions. And last, but not least, the nurture of the ethos where the efforts of teachers are appreciated and fostering independence and self-development can, over time, diminish burnout.

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